

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF CERAMIC-MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: A constitutive law is proposed for Ceramic–Matrix Composites which models matrix–cracking, sliding, fiber–breakage, and fiber pull–out. These different mechanisms induce loss of stiffness, inelastic strains, hysteresis loops, and crack closure. The features are analyzed within the framework of Continuum Damage Mechanics by the introduction of physical internal variables identified previously in material science investigations. The procedure is applied to a SiC/SiC [0/90] laminate. The description is applied to some structural problems including a plate in tension penetrated by a hole and subjected to tension and the Iosipesco specimen subjected to shear. It is observed that the SiC/SiC has the ability to redistribute stress so that the presence of stress concentrations does not compromise the performance of the component.

KEYWORDS: ceramic-matrix composite, matrix cracking, stress redistribution

INTRODUCTION

Composites consisting of a ceramic matrix reinforced by continuous ceramic fibers (CMC) are candidates for application in components which operate at temperatures in excess of those which are normal for metallic structures. In spite of the fact that the constituents of the CMC are both brittle it has been demonstrated by Aveston et al. [1971] that following matrix–cracking, sliding occurs at the fiber–matrix interface which causes inelastic deformations. The presence of matrix cracks and inelastic deformations may impart to the material the ability to redistribute stresses. The ability to redistribute stress is an important property since design studies indicate that working stresses for CMC components are sufficiently high for matrix–cracking to be unavoidable in regions of stress concentration occurring at the junctions and penetrations which are a feature of engineering components.

The intention then of the present study is to develop a continuum description of the damage processes which is mechanism–based and which may be used to describe the behavior of Ceramic–Matrix Composites (CMCs) under the conditions of multiaxial stress occurring in practice. Since crack spacing at saturation is small [Beyerley et al., 1992] in most CMCs, Continuum Damage Mechanics is an appropriate means of describing degradation since changes in elastic moduli measured on a macroscopic level provide a simpler and more robust means of measuring damage than does microscopic measurement of crack density, which requires the average of many readings before reliable values are established [Jansson & Leckie, 1993].

By combining Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) [Lemaitre, 1992] with micromechanical studies which are mechanism-based constitutive equations are developed which lend themselves to the finite element procedures commonly used in practice. The CDM formulation applied to reinforced composites is written within the framework of the Thermodynamics of Irreversible Processes [Coleman & Gurtin, 1967; Rice, 1971; Germain et al., 1983]. The first step in establishing such a model is to identify the internal variables which define the state of the material. The second is to determine the expression of the state potential in terms of the state variables and the third one to define the evolution laws of the internal variables.

The model is integrated into a finite element system (ABAQUS) and is used to estimate the behavior of a beam subjected to four point bending and a plate subjected to tensile stress which has been penetrated by a hole. The calculations have been performed using data for a SiC/SiC.

THE TENSILE STRESS–STRAIN RELATIONSHIP FOR UNIDIRECTIONAL CMCS

The results of loading / partial unloading tensile tests on SiC/SiC composites have the form shown in Fig 1. Compared to the initial elastic modulus the unloading modulus is substantially less. Plastic straining is also observed but the magnitude is usually quite modest. Post-mortem analyses of broken specimens indicate the presence of arrays of microcracks in the matrix which are accompanied by debonding and friction at the fiber–matrix interface. Matrix–cracking is responsible for the decrease of stiffness observed in experiments on CMCS and release of residual stresses due to processing, and sliding at the fiber–matrix interface is the source of irreversible deformation.

Fig 1 Typical Stress/Strain

Fig 2 Unit Cell

The cell model illustrated in Fig. 2 was first proposed by Aveston and Kelly (1971). In the unit cell shown in Fig. 2 the elastic moduli of the fiber and matrix are E_f and E_m , respectively, the volume fraction of the fiber is f and R_f is the fiber radius. The elastic modulus of the

undamaged composite is $E = f E_f + (1-f) E_m$ and average distance between cracks is denoted by $2L$. The debond length at the fiber/matrix interface is $2l_d$, and the interface is assumed to have a constant shear strength τ whose value is unknown at this stage. Residual stresses are introduced during processing so that the residual stresses ρ in the matrix is an additional unknown.

If the initial behavior of the elementary cell is isotropic and elastic, and Young's modulus is E , it can be shown that the stiffness loss depends on the crack density defined as $\pi a^2 / 4LW$ where W is the width of the element. By assuming plane stress conditions, and that the crack interactions can be neglected, a first approximation for the reduced elastic modulus \tilde{E} can be written as

$$\frac{\tilde{E}}{E} = \frac{1}{1 + 2 \frac{\pi a^2}{4LW}}$$

This relationship can be recast in the framework of CDM as

$$\frac{\tilde{E}}{E} = 1 - D$$

where

$$(1) \quad D = \frac{2 \frac{\pi a^2}{4LW}}{1 + 2 \frac{\pi a^2}{4LW}}$$

is the damage variable associated with the crack density. When D is small, a first order solution to Eq. (1) is given by

$$D \approx 2 \frac{\pi a^2}{4LW}$$

so that the damage variable is proportional to the crack density.

The internal elastic energy density in the unit cell [Hild et al., 1996] can be found by using the two step approach introduced by Volterra [1907]. The first step is to calculate the contribution of debonding and sliding at the interface using the 'cut and paste' approach in which the unbroken part (2) is moved with respect to the broken part (1) by an amount Δ_s over a length l_F (Fig3). Because of interfacial sliding, this displacement Δ_s gives rise to a self-balanced linear stress field along a length l_F in parts (1) and (2) when the interfacial behavior is assumed to be characterized by a constant shear strength. By integration over l_F and then averaging over the total length L , the elastic energy density associated with this process is given by

$$\psi^s = \frac{2}{3} \frac{fE_1(1-f)E_2}{E} \left\{ \frac{\Delta_s}{l_F} \right\}^2 \frac{l_F}{L}$$

The crack opening displacement Δ_s due to slip induces an irreversible or inelastic strain α expressed as

$$\alpha = \frac{fE_1}{E} \frac{\Delta_s}{L}$$

The second step consists of an elastic loading of the damaged system so that the elastic energy density is given by

$$(2) \quad \psi^e = \frac{1}{2} E (1-D) (\bar{\varepsilon} - \alpha)^2$$

where the current elastic modulus is $E (1-D)$.

The total elastic energy density is then the sum of the two elements of the energy densities so that

$$(3) \quad \psi = \frac{1}{2} E (1-D) (\bar{\varepsilon} - \alpha)^2 + \frac{2}{3} \frac{fE_1(1-f)E_2}{E} \left\{ \frac{\Delta_s}{l_F} \right\}^2 \frac{l_F}{L}$$

For convenience the energy density can be expressed in a more compact form by using state variables which are the total strain $\bar{\varepsilon}$, the damage variable D modeling the loss of stiffness due to the cracking mechanism, the inelastic strain α derived previously, and the damage variable $d = 3fE_1 l_F/4(1-f)E_2$ which defines the size of the slip zone related to the average crack spacing. The elastic energy density in terms of the new internal variables is [Hild et al., 1996]

$$(3) \quad \psi = \frac{1}{2} E (1-D) (\bar{\varepsilon} - \alpha)^2 + \frac{1}{2} E \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{d} \right)$$

The forces associated with the state variables $(\bar{\varepsilon}, D, d, \alpha)$ are respectively given by

$$(4.1) \quad \bar{\sigma} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \bar{\varepsilon}} = E (1-D) (\bar{\varepsilon} - \alpha)$$

$$(4.2) \quad Y = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial D} = \frac{E}{2} (\bar{\varepsilon} - \alpha)^2$$

$$(4.3) \quad y = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial d} = \frac{E}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha}{d} \right)^2$$

$$(4.4) \quad X = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \alpha} = -\bar{\sigma} + E \frac{\alpha}{d}$$

The associated forces are used to define the relevant forces driving each mechanism. Matrix cracking is assumed to be driven by Y , which plays an identical role as the energy release rate G in the framework of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics. From a micromechanical analysis [Hild et al., 1996], it can be shown that the back-stress is dependent on the applied stress $\bar{\sigma}$. therefore the driving force of the inelastic strains can be taken as the stresses acting in the same direction. The same assumption can be made when the evolution of the damage variable d related to sliding is analyzed, i.e. the driving force of d can be chosen to be its associated force y , or the applied stress $\bar{\sigma}$.

In the present approach the growth laws of the internal variables (D, d, α) are established from macroscopic quantities measured in the course of unloading and reloading sequences. To this end use is made of the solution of the response of the unit cell (Fig. 2) when subjected to an unloading/reloading sequence during which the magnitude of the shear stress remains constant.

The expressions obtained from the analysis for the residual stress ρ_1 and the internal variables D, d, α in terms of the macroscopic quantities shown in Fig. 1 are given respectively by [Hild et al., 1996]

$$(5.1) \quad \frac{-\rho_1}{E} = \left(\sqrt{\frac{\bar{\epsilon}_{in} + 2\delta\bar{\epsilon}}{4\delta\bar{\epsilon}}} - 1 \right) (\bar{\epsilon}_M - \bar{\epsilon}_{in} - 2\delta\bar{\epsilon})$$

$$(5.2) \quad D = \frac{\bar{\epsilon}_M \bar{D} - \bar{\epsilon}_{in} \bar{D} - 2\delta\bar{\epsilon}}{\bar{\epsilon}_M - \bar{\epsilon}_{in} - 2\delta\bar{\epsilon}}$$

$$(5.3) \quad \frac{d}{4} = \frac{\sqrt{(\bar{\epsilon}_{in} + 2\delta\bar{\epsilon})\delta\bar{\epsilon}}}{\bar{\epsilon}_M - \bar{\epsilon}_{in} - 2\delta\bar{\epsilon}}$$

$$(5.4) \quad \alpha = \frac{d}{2} \frac{\bar{\sigma}_M - \rho_1(1-D)}{E(1-D)}$$

where $-\rho_1 E_1 / E$ is the residual stress in the broken layer (1). Equations (5) are only valid when a constant shear strength characterizes the interfacial behavior, and lastly Eqn. (5.4) is only valid for monotonic loading conditions.

By performing a series of unloading/reloading sequences the internal variables can be determined from experiment using Eqns (5). The residual stress ρ_1 is calculated from Eqn. (5.1) and it is a test of the effectiveness of the model that the same value of the residual stress is obtained for each loading sequence. The values of D and d are given by applying Eqns (5.2) and (5.3) respectively. The information is now available to complete the calculation for Eqn. (5.4). The corresponding associated forces are obtained by the expressions given in Eqns. (4). The relationship between the internal variables and the associated forces can then be

investigated by knowing the driving forces of each state variable. It is this method which is proposed to model the behavior of CMC laminates.

CMCS WITH MULTIDIRECTIONAL FIBER SYSTEMS

The one-dimensional investigation can be extended to a [0/90] laminate composite and to a [0/90] woven composite subjected to multiaxial plane stress states by establishing first the properties of each layer and then using laminate analysis.

The components of each layer consist of the matrix, the fiber and the interface, with f being the fiber volume fraction. The fiber direction defines the 1–2 axes. The axes x – y correspond to the principal axes of the strains in the ceramic matrix. The definition of the axes used at the constituent, layer and composite levels are shown in Fig. 4. For the case of a 0/90 symmetric layup Burr et al (1996) have established that the free energy has the expression

$$(6) \quad \psi = \frac{1}{2} (\underline{\underline{\epsilon}} - \underline{\underline{\alpha}}) : \underline{\underline{E}}(D_{my}^{00}, D_{my}^{90}, D_{fl}^{00}, D_{fl}^{90}) : (\underline{\underline{\epsilon}} - \underline{\underline{\alpha}}) + \psi^S(\underline{\underline{\alpha}}, \underline{\underline{d}})$$

Fig 4 Orientation of axes

where D_{my}^{00} , D_{my}^{90} are the matrix damage parameters and $D_f = \{D_{fl}^{00}; D_{fl}^{90}\}$ is the set of damage variables modeling fiber-breakage in the 0 and 90 plies respectively. The interface slip parameters are $\underline{\underline{d}} = \{d_{11}; d_{22}; d_{12}\}$

Finite Element Analysis

The resulting constitutive equations have been introduced into a UMAT routine of the finite element code ABAQUS (Hibbitt et al 1993). Early calculations of beams in four-point bending, proved to be simple to run, and indicated the ability of the CMC to redistribute stress and agreed with experimental observation that elastic calculations are very conservative. Components which were more challenging were the Iosipescu specimen (Fig 5) and a plate, penetrated by a hole, subjected to a tensile stress parallel to the fiber directions.

When the availability of materials is restricted to planar form shear data data is to subject the Iosipescu to shear loads specimen [Iosipescu, 1967]. The shear properties of the material are obtained by plotting the average stress at the minimum section against the shear strain measured by strain gauges placed at the center of the specimen.

Fig 5: The Iosipescu specimen

It is known that the shear stress at the minimum section of this specimen is sensibly constant when the material is elastic and isotropic, but it is not known if the constant shear stress assumption is valid when cracking occurs. In addition to verifying the suitability of the Iosipescu specimen for obtaining the properties of materials which crack as illustrated in Fig, the tests provide an opportunity to measure the ability of the constitutive equations to predict the behavior of a component in which the stress state is different from those used in the identification procedure.

Fig 6: Stress distribution at minimum section

The prediction of the average stress against strain at the center of the specimen is agrees with the experimental observations to within 5%. The results of the finite element analysis shown in Fig. 6 indicate that the shear stress at the minimum section is essentially constant therefore justifying the use of the Iosipescu specimen as a means of obtaining shear data. Experiments on plates in tension which are penetrated by holes suggest that strength is dictated by the nett cross section and that the effect of the initial elastic stress concentration is minimised by the stress redistribution due to matrix cracking. The calculations indicate because of stress redistribution that almost half of the ligament stress carries the same stress. The elastic stress concentration factor is 4.1 which following the effects of stress redistribution reduces to 2.4. The large effect of matrix cracking is evident.

CONCLUSIONS

A CDM model is proposed for CMCs which is mechanisms-based. The laws which relate the growth of the internal state variables to their associated forces have been derived from the unloading-reloading paths during tensile experiments for two different directions. The ability of the model to predict the response to another state of stress suggests the advantage of a mechanism-based approach.

When applied to SiC/SiC [0/90] lay-ups, the present model has 10 internal variables, viz. three inelastic strains modeling sliding, three damage variables describing the amount of debonding and four damage variables accounting for matrix-cracking and fiber-breakage in the two plies. It is shown that only two different experiments in tension are needed to identify the growth laws of the ten internal variables. The model has the potential to be applied to other material configurations (e.g., SiC/CAS, SiC/C, C/C, and presumably SiC/Al₂O₃) and architectures (e.g., woven configurations). Furthermore, the general framework presented herein has been applied to room temperature configurations and monotonic loading conditions. However extensions to cyclic load histories as well as high temperature applications can be included with minimal change to the state potential formulations. Evolution laws will have to be modified slightly.

The reliability of the Iosipescu test is confirmed as a means of average stress-strain shear data, and the constitutive equations are able to predict the shear properties correctly. However, it is shown that the average shear properties may be slightly different from the actual stress-strain shear data in the center of the ligament. Therefore the identification of the shear properties based upon the measurements on an Iosipescu test are, strictly speaking, only an approximation of the actual response in pure shear.

The ability of stress redistribution due to the non-linearity of the stress/strain curve has been shown in the case of the Iosipescu experiment. Stress redistribution important for structural applications has been demonstrated for beam bending and tensile plate penetrated by holes.

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